

REVIEW ARTICLE

Human talent management: the key to boosting workplace productivity

Gestión del talento humano: clave para potenciar la productividad laboral

Teresa M. Roldán

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Abstract This review article examines the relationship between human talent management and labor productivity, emphasizing its strategic impact on organizational performance. Using a narrative and analytical approach, it explores recent literature linking HR practices, such as recruitment, training, performance evaluation, and employee motivation, to efficiency, satisfaction, and retention improvements. Case studies from both public and private sectors reveal how effective talent management directly influences service quality, innovation, and business competitiveness. The article presents key models by Cuesta, Morales Cartaya, Werther and Davis, and Harper and Lynch, highlighting their perspectives on talent development. It also organizes and analyzes critical indicators in five areas: hiring, compensation, employability, training, and occupational safety. The findings show that strategic human talent management is essential for increasing productivity across various organizational contexts. The review identifies research gaps and suggests future lines of inquiry to reinforce the connection between human development and organizational success.

Keywords human talent management, labor productivity, organizational performance, management models, HR indicators.

Resumen Este artículo de revisión analiza la relación entre la gestión del talento humano y la productividad laboral, considerando su impacto estratégico en el desempeño organizacional. A través de un enfoque narrativo y analítico, se examina literatura reciente que vincula prácticas de gestión como selección, capacitación, evaluación y motivación del personal con mejoras en la eficiencia, satisfacción y retención laboral. Se revisaron estudios de casos en sectores públicos y privados que evidencian cómo una administración adecuada del capital humano influye directamente en la calidad del servicio, la innovación y la competitividad empresarial. Además, se presentan modelos relevantes como los de Cuesta, Morales Cartaya, Werther y Davis, y Harper y Lynch, destacando sus enfoques sobre el desarrollo del talento. El artículo también clasifica e interpreta indicadores clave en cinco áreas: contratación, compensación, empleabilidad, formación y seguridad laboral. Se concluye que una gestión estratégica del talento humano es fundamental para impulsar la productividad en contextos organizacionales diversos. Finalmente, se identifican brechas en la literatura y se proponen líneas de investigación futura que contribuyan a fortalecer la vinculación entre el desarrollo humano y el éxito empresarial.

Palabras clave gestión del talento humano, productividad laboral, desempeño organizacional, modelos de gestión, indicadores de recursos humanos.

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✉ Teresa M. Roldán
troldan6645@utm.edu.ec

Universidad Técnica de Manabí, Ecuador.

Introduction

Human talent management is an essential component of today's organizations, as it directly influences employee productivity, business competitiveness, and sustainability. In a dynamic and globalized environment, it is crucial to implement effective strategies to attract, develop, retain, and motivate staff, thereby optimizing both individual and organizational performance. Various studies have shown that proper human talent management improves key factors such as job satisfaction, operational efficiency, and employee retention, strengthening business success (Chiavenato, 2009).

According to Vera (2021), in his study entitled "Human talent management and customer service", the influence of human talent management on the quality of service provided by the seven de Noviembre Interprovincial Transport Cooperative in the Paján canton is analyzed. The main objective of the research was to determine to what extent human talent management impacts customer service and how this relationship influences the profitability and sustainability of the cooperative.

The study highlights that efficient human talent management improves service quality and acts as a strategic driver for attracting new users and optimizing the use of human resources. To this end, a mixed-methods approach was adopted, combining qualitative and quantitative methods in a descriptive and correlational design. A structured survey was administered to a sample of 244 users in the Paján canton, allowing key data to be collected on service perceptions and their relationship with human talent management.

The results indicated that the cooperative maintains an adequate and satisfactory level of customer service, which contributes to maintaining its quality standards and achieving organizational objectives. However, the study suggests that improved staff training and motivational strategies could further enhance the user experience and strengthen the company's competitiveness in the interprovincial transportation sector.

For Quiroz (2019), who prepared a study called "Human talent management and its relationship with organizational performance in the collaborators of the Regional Directorate of Transport and Communications of Tacna", talks about the challenge that companies currently face to be more efficient and effective, whose general objective is to determine if there is a relationship between human talent management and the importance it has to optimize organizational performance. The research used the descriptive correlational method with a non-experimental design. The study applied a structured survey with a sample of 152 employees, whose

results showed that the company develops good human talent management and that good organizational development of collaborators in the institution is appreciated. Finally, it was concluded that there is a significant relationship of 95% between human talent management and organizational performance.

According to Tamay (2021), in the preparation of his final postgraduate project entitled "Human talent management and its impact on the labor productivity of the Regional Government of La Libertad, 2020", whose main objective is to determine whether human talent management impacts the labor productivity of the Regional Government of La Libertad, applying a type of non-experimental casual correlational research, which is based on descriptive statistics that allows us to consider that human talent management is regular and labor productivity is average.

Studying the relationship between human talent management and labor productivity is crucial for companies seeking to optimize their resources and improve organizational performance. Despite the extensive literature available, gaps in our comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence this relationship persist, especially in specific sectors such as transportation and services. This review seeks to consolidate knowledge about the most effective human talent management strategies and their impact on productivity. It offers a critical analysis that serves as a basis for future research and applications in the organizational field.

This review article analyzes the existing literature on human talent management and its impact on labor productivity, assessing the main theories, models, and strategies applied in this field. It also aims to identify current trends and their relationship with organizational performance to determine gaps and opportunities for future research in this field.

This study adopts a narrative review approach, with a descriptive and analytical design, to synthesize existing information on human talent management and its impact on labor productivity. Narrative reviews allow for critically examining the available literature, identifying trends, commonalities, and divergences from previous research. Unlike systematic reviews or meta-analyses, this type of study does not follow a rigid source selection protocol. Instead, it analyzes relevant information to understand the phenomenon and provide a comprehensive view of the topic.

To gather information, various academic databases and open-access repositories, such as Scopus, Google Scholar, Redalyc, and SciELO, were consulted, prioritizing articles published in the last five years. Keywords such as "human

talent management”, “work productivity”, “organizational performance”, “work efficiency”, and “human resource strategies” were used, using Boolean operators to refine the search. Inclusion criteria included content relevance, methodological rigor of the studies, and their applicability to different business sectors. Sources lacking empirical support or whose information was not relevant to the study were excluded.

The literature review was conducted through a thematic classification of the studies found, organizing them into categories such as human talent management strategies, labor productivity models, the impact of training and development on organizational performance, and trends in talent retention. A critical evaluation of the findings was then conducted, highlighting the main similarities among the studies and identifying gaps in the literature. This process allowed for a well-founded and contextualized discussion, facilitating the formulation of recommendations for future research and implementing strategies within the organizational sphere.

Development of the theoretical framework

Human resource management encompasses the processes of selecting people to lead and manage these organizations, which promote local development. People with specialized skills, competencies, and attitudes are necessary at the strategic and operational levels for sound decision-making and for executing assigned tasks (Jara et al., 2018, cited by Anastacio et al., 2020, p. 437).

Human resource management (HRM) is an interdisciplinary area: it includes concepts of industrial and organizational psychology, organizational sociology, industrial engineering, labor law, safety engineering, occupational medicine, systems engineering, computer science, etc. The issues that are usually dealt with in the area of HRM are related to an enormous multiplicity of fields of knowledge: we talk about the application and interpretation of psychological tests and interviews, technology of individual learning and organizational changes, nutrition and food, medicine and nursing, social service, life and career plans, work design, organizational structure and culture, job satisfaction, absenteeism, salaries and social expenses, market, leisure, fires and accidents, discipline and attitudes, interpretation of labor laws, efficiency and effectiveness, statistics and records, transportation for staff, responsibility at the supervisory level, auditing and countless other diverse issues (Chiavenato, 2009).

Therefore, talent management is behind every decision made within the company regarding personnel and all their activities, from designing a campaign for a product or ser-

vice to producing and distributing it, monitoring its quality, and allocating resources to each of the company’s processes (Zayas, 1996).

Basic definition of human talent management

Table 1 presents a synthesis of key conceptual definitions related to Human Resource Management (HRM) and Talent Management (TM) proposed by various authors. These definitions provide a theoretical foundation for understanding the strategic importance of managing human capital within organizations. The reviewed literature highlights the evolution of HRM from an operational function to a strategic driver focused on developing core competencies, enhancing employee motivation, and generating competitive advantages. Additionally, the concepts underscore the integration of processes aimed at attracting, developing, and retaining talent, as well as fostering a positive organizational environment aligned with business objectives.

Human talent management is a key area of organizational management, focused on attracting, developing, retaining, and motivating staff to improve their performance and productivity. Over the years, various authors have defined this concept from different perspectives:

- Chiavenato (2009) highlights that human talent management has evolved towards a more strategic approach, focusing on creating and applying organizational knowledge to generate competitive advantages.
- Barceló (2019) defines talent management as a set of integrated human resources processes designed to attract and retain talent, thus solving problems of turnover and shortage of qualified personnel.
- Pizarro et al. (2019) emphasize that human talent management involves workers’ incorporation, development, and retention, which is closely linked to work motivation.
- Chávez (2018) argues that talent management is based on the strategic direction of human capital and competency management, using methodologies that promote professional development inside and outside work.
- Flores et al. (2018) emphasize that human talent management should focus on generating competitive advantages through the organization and optimization of internal processes.
- López et al. (2017) propose that human talent management is an administrative unit that organizes and executes activities to satisfy personnel needs and improve the organizational structure.

In general, all authors agree that proper human talent management optimizes employee performance and strengthens companies’ competitiveness by ensuring the alignment of

Table 1. Concepts of human talent management

Author	Concept
Chiavenato (2009)	Human resource management (HRM) is a relatively new field of study that has undergone and is undergoing profound changes and transformations. Its role is expanding and becoming more strategic and less operational. Its objectives are increasingly focused on the organization's business and introducing competitive advantages through creating, developing, disseminating, and applying corporate knowledge in the form of skills essential to business success. Increasingly, HRM addresses intangible assets that not only enhance human capital but also directly result in the consolidation and growth of the intellectual capital acquired by the organization.
Barcelo (2019)	Talent management (TMM) is a set of integrated human resources processes designed to attract, develop, motivate, and retain an organization's employees, primarily to address employee retention issues.
Pizarro et al. (2019)	Human talent management is a process that recruits, develops, and retains employees. In contrast, employee motivation refers to the force that drives and empowers employees to begin, maintain, and improve their assigned roles.
Chávez (2018)	Human talent management is based on the strategic management of human capital, competency management, and a human resource management methodology to approach the concept of talent. It consists of methods for developing competencies within the workplace, methods for developing competencies outside the workplace, and techniques for developing competencies.
Flores et al. (2018)	The role of the human talent department within companies is to organize and contribute to creating competitive advantages that allow them to differentiate themselves from the competition. To do this, they must clearly define processes, organize actions and activities to interact responsibly in a technological world, employ the necessary resources for their implementation, and achieve a positive work environment, safeguarding well-being and enhancing good labor relations under the country's statutory standards.
López et al. (2017)	Human talent management is the administrative unit responsible for staff interaction within and outside the organization. Activities are organized and executed to meet the requirements established within the management and structuring of the area's processes, from the initial to the macro level.
Pérez (2016)	Talent management, or human capital management, is an integrated set of organizational processes designed to attract, manage, develop, motivate, and retain employees. In other words, this practice is based on achieving better business results with each employee's collaboration. The strategy is executed by striking a balance between the professional development of employees, the human focus, and the achievement of organizational goals.

organizational objectives with employee development.

Human talent management is the strategic process by which an organization plans, selects, develops, and retains its human capital to maximize productivity and ensure sustainability. This approach integrates recruitment, training, performance evaluation, and employee well-being practices to align individual employee growth with organizational goals. Effective human talent management improves the work environment and employee satisfaction, and boosts operational efficiency and business competitiveness.

Objectives and functions of the human talent management area

The human resource management (HRM) area consists of planning, organizing, developing, coordinating, and con-

trolling techniques capable of promoting efficient staff performance. At the same time, the organization constitutes the means that allows the people who collaborate within it to achieve their objectives, directly or indirectly related to work (Chiavenato, 2009).

The functions of human talent management are as follows (Aular, 2021, p. 7):

- Human talent planning;
- Recruitment and selection;
- Training and development;
- Assessment;
- Proper allocation of people to jobs;
- Feedback;
- Compensation and labor legality;

- Staff relations with the organization;
- Guide change processes;
- Activity assignments;
- Manage disciplinary actions

Indicators for human talent management

Human talent management indicators are fundamental tools for evaluating the performance of an organization's internal processes. They enable organizations to measure, diagnose, and improve efficiency in human capital management. Through these indicators, companies can make informed decisions that contribute to achieving their strategic objectives, optimizing resources, and strengthening employee productivity.

In human talent management, the most relevant indicators are grouped into five main categories, regardless of the company's size or the economic sector in which it operates. These indicators allow for monitoring the efficiency of hiring, compensation, employability, training, and job security processes, ensuring a comprehensive approach to personnel management.

1. Hiring indicators

Talent recruitment is a key process within any organization, as it defines the quality of the personnel who will join the company. The following indicators are used to measure its effectiveness:

- **Average time to hire:** This allows you to assess how quickly the human resources department recruits talent to fill vacancies, which is crucial to avoid disrupting the company's operations. A long time to hire can indicate problems in the selection process or a talent shortage in the market.
- **Cost per hire:** Measures the expense of hiring a new employee, including advertising, selection tests, interviews, and initial training.
- **Job Fit Index:** Evaluates the degree of fit between the selected candidate's profile and the job requirements, determining the effectiveness of the selection process.

2. Compensation Indicators

Compensation and incentives have a direct impact on employee satisfaction and retention. The following indicators are used to measure their effectiveness:

- **Overtime Surcharges:** Represents the percentage of overtime hours spent on base pay. Analyzing these surcharges helps determine whether the use of overtime hours is essential or reflects deficiencies in operational planning.
- **Pay equity:** Measures the difference in salaries between employees with similar roles, ensuring fairness

in compensation and avoiding pay gaps that could affect staff motivation.

- **Compensation Satisfaction Index:** This index evaluates employees' level of satisfaction with their salary and benefits, which influences their performance and loyalty to the company.

3. Employability indicators

Talent stability and retention are essential for reducing operating costs and improving knowledge continuity within the organization. Key indicators in this category include:

- **Employee turnover:** Measures the number of employees who leave the company in a given period. High turnover can indicate organizational culture problems, talent management deficiencies, or dissatisfaction with working conditions.
- **Average tenure:** Analyzes the average time an employee remains with the organization, allowing for the evaluation of the success of retention and employee well-being strategies.
- **Voluntary termination rate:** Indicates the number of employees who leave the company voluntarily. Analyzing the reasons behind these resignations is crucial to identifying opportunities for improving organizational culture.
- **Absenteeism rate:** This assesses the frequency of employees missing work without a valid justification. This may be related to health problems, lack of motivation, or job dissatisfaction.

4. Training and development indicators

Human talent development is key to innovation and continuous improvement. Training indicators measure the impact of training programs on employees' professional growth.

- **Training program attendance:** Measures the percentage of employees who participate in training sessions organized by the company.
- **Internal promotion rate:** Reflects the percentage of promotions within the organization, indicating the success of training in developing internal talent.
- **Satisfaction with training programs:** Evaluates employees' perceptions of the quality and usefulness of the training received.
- **Return on investment in training (ROI):** This measure determines the financial impact of training on worker productivity and efficiency.

5. Occupational health and safety indicators

Ensuring employee safety and well-being is a fundamental pillar of human talent management. To achieve this, the following indicators are used:

- **Medical disability absenteeism rate:** Measures the

number of days missed due to work-related illness or accident. A high absenteeism rate may indicate problems with working conditions or a lack of preventive measures.

- **Accident rate:** Represents the number of workplace accidents in a given period. Its analysis helps identify risks and improve prevention policies.
- **Severity index:** This index evaluates the number of work days lost due to occupational accidents or illnesses. A high index may indicate deficiencies in workplace safety management.
- **Safety compliance level:** Measures the company's compliance with legal regulations regarding occupational health and safety.

Using metrics in human talent management allows companies to measure the performance of their recruitment, compensation, retention, training, and job security strategies. By monitoring these metrics, organizations can identify areas for improvement, optimize productivity, and strengthen their competitiveness in the marketplace. Implementing an effective measurement system contributes to staff development and directly impacts the company's sustainability and success.

Human talent management models

In a highly competitive and constantly evolving business environment, human talent management has evolved from a purely administrative function to a fundamental strategic pillar of organizational sustainability. A company's ability to attract, develop, retain, and enhance its human capital is crucial to its long-term performance and success. In this context, human talent management models have emerged as key tools for structuring and optimizing personnel management, aligning their skills and motivations with organizational objectives.

Over the years, various theories and approaches have shaped these models, adapting to changing market needs and modern work dynamics. From traditional approaches based on human resource management to the most innovative strategies that integrate technology, data analytics, and competency management, each model offers a unique insight into how to maximize the potential of talent within an organization. Understanding these models is not only essential for human resource leaders and managers, but also for any professional seeking to optimize their performance and contribute to their company's growth.

Cuesta (2005) proposes a model that incorporates significant improvements by placing the individual at the center of its human resources subsystems and policies, considered as an end rather than a means. Education and development are essential references for the remaining subsystems and poli-

cies, which will include all key processes and activities.

The model by Cuesta (2005) represents an innovative approach to human talent management. It places people at the center of organizational processes, considering them not only as a productive resource but also as an end in themselves. This model proposes a more humanistic and strategic vision, in which human talent management is directly linked to the development of people and the generation of sustainable competitive advantages for the organization.

Main features of the model by Cuesta (2005)

1. Focus on human capital:

Unlike traditional models focused on resource management, Cuesta's model emphasizes the importance of developing employees' competencies, skills, and knowledge, enhancing their personal and professional growth.

2. Integrated human talent management subsystems:

The model proposes comprehensive management of human talent through interconnected subsystems, which include:

- Recruitment and selection with a focus on person-position fit.
- Training and development are key elements for organizational learning.
- Performance evaluation and feedback, promoting a system of continuous improvement.
- Compensation and recognition systems are designed to motivate and retain talent.

3. Link with the organizational strategy:

Cuesta's model emphasizes that human talent management should not be an isolated area within the company but should be aligned with the organization's vision, mission, and strategic objectives.

4. Importance of education and personal development:

Unlike other models that focus only on immediate productivity, this model emphasizes education and continuous learning as fundamental pillars for the evolution of the organization and its human capital.

5. Ethics and corporate social responsibility (CSR):

The model incorporates principles of ethics and social responsibility, ensuring that human talent management contributes to the well-being of employees and the community.

6. Applicability and benefits

This model has been applied in various organizations to improve employee productivity and job satisfaction. Its holistic approach allows companies to develop highly engaged human talent aligned with organizational values.

The model by Cuesta (2005) offers an innovative perspective on human talent management by integrating strategic,

educational, and ethical aspects. Its application allows organizations to optimize work performance, strengthen their organizational culture, and ensure sustained growth over time.

The model by Morales (2009) is a comprehensive and strategic human talent management approach developed through applied research in various Cuban organizations. This model seeks to optimize human capital management by implementing a comprehensive system continuously improving organizational performance. Morales (2009) argues that, to achieve effective talent management, it is essential to consider the organizational context and the external factors that influence employee behavior.

This model emerged from a study conducted by the Ministry of Labor and Social Security of the Republic of Cuba between 2003 and 2005 among more than 3,000 business entities. This study explained the need to implement a human capital management system. Hernández then worked to implement the model under the name Cuban Model of Integrated Human Capital Management.

Main Features of the model by Morales (2009)

1. Integrated human capital management approach:

This model proposes that human talent management should be approached holistically, connecting all key human resources processes (recruitment, training, compensation, evaluation, etc.) within a coherent system that supports the organization's strategic objectives.

Human talent management must be aligned with the organization's vision, mission, and strategic objectives to ensure that all efforts are focused on improving organizational performance.

2. Systemic and competence vision:

Morales (2009) argues that human talent management must be viewed from a systemic perspective, recognizing that human talent is a system within the organization that interacts with other subsystems.

The model emphasizes the development of key competencies for each position, creating competency profiles that allow organizations to identify and foster the skills needed in each employee for the company's success.

This model benefits organizations seeking a strategic, long-term approach to human talent management. Its application offers several key benefits that help companies improve operational efficiency and employee satisfaction.

The model by Morales (2009) presents a comprehensive and strategic approach to human talent management based on aligning human resources processes with the organizational strategy and developing key competencies. This model improves the efficiency of internal processes and contributes to creating a positive work environment and continuous

innovation within the organization. Its implementation allows companies to strengthen their human capital and ensure outstanding organizational performance.

Werther and Davis (2014) Human Resources Management Model is one of the most widely used references in human talent management. It offers a structured and systemic approach to managing human capital within organizations. This model recognizes employees as a company's most valuable asset and proposes management based on interrelated subsystems, which must be coordinated to achieve efficient talent management. Each human capital activity constitutes a subsystem directly related to all other activities (Werther & Davis, 2014, p. 15).

In practice, systems models help identify the basic variables. After considering new information as input, specialists determine the desired output. Once the inputs and outputs are known, decision makers use their knowledge of human capital management to achieve the desired results most efficiently. They often obtain feedback to verify whether they are achieving success (Werther & Davis, 2014, p. 15).

Beer and colleagues' HRM model integrated all key HRM activities into four areas with the same names as those policies. This model explains that employee influence (participation, involvement) is central, affecting the remaining areas of HR policies: Work System, Human Resource Flow, and Reward Systems (Aduna et al., 2017).

This model uses a strategic, participatory, and humanistic human resources vision. It proposes that human resources decisions should consider multiple contextual factors and focus on economic results and long-term consequences for individuals, the organization, and society.

Model-based on the fact that the organization requires Human Resources in a certain quantity and quality, Human Resources Management allows for satisfying this demand by carrying out activities that begin with the personnel inventory and evaluating human potential (Aduna et al., 2017).

The Harper and Lynch Model (1992) provides a solid and efficient framework for human talent management, with an approach based on planning, control, and operational efficiency. Its application allows organizations to manage their human capital in an orderly manner, ensuring that the most qualified person fills each position and that human talent processes are continuously evaluated.

However, in today's environment, where flexibility, innovation, and organizational culture play a fundamental role in attracting and retaining talent, this model can be complemented with more modern approaches, including competency management, motivation, and digital transformation in human talent management.

The study of models and their application in organizations

must be integrated into the strategic management of human resources, defined as those activities that affect the behavior of people when formulating and implementing company strategies or decisions regarding the orientation given to human resource management processes and that affect the behavior of individuals in the medium and long term, taking as a reference both internal and contextual factors of the organization (López et al., 2022, p. 28).

A paired comparison of the human talent management models analyzed: Cuesta (2005), Morales Cartaya (2009), Werther and Davis (2014), and Harper and Lynch (1992). The comparison focuses on five key criteria.

Table 2 presents a comparative analysis of various theoretical approaches to human talent management, based on paired comparisons between prominent authors in the field. The table highlights differences and similarities across five analytical dimensions: general approach, vision of human talent, level of integration, applicability, and strategic orientation. This comparison provides insight into how each model conceptualizes human talent—as a developmental objective, strategic asset, or functional resource—and reveals the degree to which these models align with the evolving needs of modern organizations. The contrasts also emphasize the adaptability of each model to specific organizational contexts, such as public institutions, private enterprises, or transformation-driven environments.

Human talent management is emerging as a key element in boosting productivity. It is about managing personnel and implementing policies and practices that align employee skills, commitment, and performance with company objectives. Processes such as effective selection, ongoing training, performance evaluation, fair compensation, and a healthy work environment are crucial for improving efficiency and quality of work.

Recent studies support that organizations that invest in strategic talent management achieve higher productivity levels, lower employee turnover, greater innovation, and better adaptation to change. Thus, the relationship between human talent management and productivity is operational and structural: people's development directly translates into organizational development. Understanding this connection is essential for formulating sustainable strategies that generate value for the company and its employees.

Basic definitions of labor productivity

Table 3 presents various definitions of labor productivity as proposed by different authors. These conceptualizations consistently emphasize productivity as a measurable relationship between the outcomes achieved and the resources utilized, highlighting its importance at both individual and

organizational levels. The definitions reflect diverse perspectives, ranging from a focus on the efficiency and effectiveness in the use of resources (Chiavenato, 2017; Robbins & Judge, 2017) to approaches that consider human factors such as motivation, effort, and work methods (Gutiérrez, 2020). This range of definitions provides a comprehensive understanding of labor productivity not only as an economic indicator but also as a reflection of overall performance within organizations.

Measuring labor productivity

Labor productivity results from various factors that impact an organization's workers. Although productivity is measured as the ratio of actual production to invested resources, it is important to remember that human resources are subject to psychological factors, not just technical or quantitative ones (Suárez et al., 2017, p. 63).

Regarding factor productivity calculations, specifically labor productivity, estimates can most often be made for the national economy, and with some degree of detail for specific productive activities such as manufacturing, trade, construction, and specific service sectors. Likewise, information exists on labor remuneration for these activities, so unit labor cost indices can also be generated. (INEGI, 2015).

Labor productivity is the relationship between the output obtained or sold and the amount of labor incorporated into the production process in a given period. Labor productivity can be measured at the level of an establishment, a company, an industry, a sector, or a country (INEGI, 2015).

There are two procedures for quantifying productivity:

$$\text{Labor productivity} = \frac{\text{Production}}{\text{Hours worked}}$$

$$\text{Labor productivity} = \frac{\text{Sales}}{\text{Hours worked}}$$

“Labor productivity can also be measured by the relationship between the quantity produced or sold and the number of workers employed (INEGI, 2015, pág. 1)”.

$$\text{Labor productivity} = \frac{\text{Production}}{\text{Number of employees}}$$

$$\text{Labor productivity} = \frac{\text{Sales}}{\text{Number of employees}}$$

This ratio allows us to evaluate an economic unit's performance over time. If the ratio between the volume produced

Table 2. Comparative analysis of human talent management approaches across key authors

Paired comparison	General approach	Vision of human talent	Level of integration	Applicability	Strategic approach
Cuesta vs. Morales Cartaya	Both are strategic and integrative, but Cuesta emphasizes human development as an end.	Cuesta sees it as the center and end of the model; Morales conceives it as strategic human capital.	Both are integrative, although Morales is more structured and systemic.	Morales is more formal for public institutions and flexible for private and social organizations.	Both have a high strategic focus, but Cuesta emphasizes the human and educational aspects more.
Cuesta vs. Werther and Davis	Cuesta is more humanistic; Werther and Davis are more operational-systemic.	Cuesta prioritizes personal development; Werther treats it as a functional organizational asset.	Werther has more defined and operational subsystems.	Werther is best suited to companies seeking efficiency; it is less suitable for those prioritizing organizational culture.	Cuesta is strategic from the perspective of education and culture; Werther is strategic from the perspective of functional management.
Cuesta vs. Harper and Lynch	Cuesta is comprehensive and modern; Harper and Lynch are more traditional and sequential.	Cuesta promotes talent as a value; Harper and Lynch are a resource to be managed.	Cuesta has a greater interrelation of processes; Harper uses linear stages.	Harper focuses on technical planning, and Cuesta focuses on strategic human development management.	Cuesta has a clear strategic focus; Harper is more technical and less strategic.
Morales Cartaya vs. Werther and Davis	structured and systemic vision.	Morales highlights talent as a driver of innovation; Werther manages it through operational efficiency.	Both integrate processes, but Morales connects more with the external environment.	Morales is better suited to changing environments; Werther is better suited to stable, hierarchical environments.	Morales is more strategic in managing change; Werther is more operational.
Morales Cartaya vs. Harper and Lynch	Morales is modern and adaptive; Harper is traditional and focused on domestic demand.	Morales promotes skills development; Harper seeks only to fill vacancies.	Morales has integrated management; Harper has fragmented and sequential processes.	Morales adapts to organizations that transform; Harper to those that maintain their structure.	Morales has a strong strategic focus; Harper lacks deep strategic vision.
Werther and Davis vs. Harper and Lynch	Werther is systemic and current; Harper is descriptive and classic.	Werther manages people as connected subsystems; Harper maps and manages them.	Werther has connected subsystems; Harper relies on sequential processes.	Werther is more versatile in different types of organizations; Harper is more useful for rigid structures.	Werther has a partial strategic focus; Harper lacks alignment with organizational strategy.

Table 3. Concept of labor productivity

Labor productivity	
Reference	Concept
Gutiérrez (2020)	Productivity relates to the results obtained in a process or system, based on the resources employed. Therefore, it is generally measured by the quotient formed by the results achieved and the resources employed. Results can be measured in units produced, parts sold, or profits, while the resources employed can be quantified by the number of workers, total time employed, machine hours, etc. In other words, productivity results are measured by properly assessing the resources employed to produce or generate specific results.
Alamar & Guijarro (2018)	Productivity, understood as the relationship between a company's resources invested in its operations and the benefits it obtains from them, is a fundamental indicator of a company's state and the quality of its management.
Robbins & Judge (2017)	Productivity is the highest level of analysis in organizational behavior; it is the organization as a whole. A company is productive if it achieves its goals by transforming inputs into outputs at the lowest cost. Therefore, productivity requires both effectiveness and efficiency.
Chiavenato (2017)	Productivity is a performance measure that includes efficiency and effectiveness. Efficiency is the appropriate use of available resources; in other words, it emphasizes resources and processes. Effectiveness is fulfilling clearly defined goals and objectives; in this case, the most important factors are the ends and results.
Mileman & Sibanda (2016)	Productivity is the effective use of innovation and resources to increase the aggregate output of products and services.

(or sold) and the amount of labor incorporated increases over time, the average product of labor has improved; if it decreases, then the average unit of labor is less productive (INEGI, 2015).

To use this method, you must measure productivity to reveal how well an employee's output contributes to the company's goals and objectives. For this to work correctly, employees must first be given clear, individual productivity goals to work toward and all the tools and information they need to achieve those goals.

Employees should meet with their supervisors regularly to discuss progress and resolve issues. Measuring productivity throughout the year helps employees stay focused on their goals.

Another method for evaluating employee productivity is to request 360-degree feedback to gather feedback from coworkers and measure an individual's productivity. This method can only be used if your organization's employees interact a lot with each other. This measure requires that an employee's productivity be evaluated by everyone with whom they work or interact daily, including those above and below their hierarchical level. The accuracy of this method relies on the fact that it evaluates a large number of people, all of whom are trained in objective feedback and all of whom influence productivity within the company.

It can be challenging to measure sales and team produc-

tivity accurately. Many factors affect a salesperson's output. Start by recording the different aspects of productivity within a given period. Those numbers may include:

- The total number of sales completed in that period.
- The total amount of sales made.
- The number of calls made to current customers.
- The number of sales made to current customers.
- The number of new customers gained
- The number of calls made to new potential customers.
- Expenses for the sale/acquisition of new customers

Customer service productivity can be measured in many ways, including:

- The time it takes for a customer to be served (such as call wait times or in-person wait times)
- The time it takes to complete a customer's order
- Customer retention rates: the percentage of customers who return at least once
- The time that these customers are retained
- The frequency with which products are returned
- How many customer complaints are received in a given period

The results analyzed in the review establish a clear and significant relationship between strategic human talent management and increased employee productivity in different

organizations. Evidence from studies conducted in the public and private sectors shows that variables such as training, motivation, performance evaluation, and work environment directly impact employee efficiency and engagement levels.

For example, Vera (2021) demonstrates that proper human talent management directly impacts the quality of customer service, which, in turn, impacts the profitability and sustainability of a transport cooperative. This coincides with Chiavenato (2019), who argues that modern HRM should generate value through skills development and the consolidation of intellectual capital.

Likewise, Quiroz (2019) establishes a significant correlation between talent management and organizational performance, supporting the postulates of Barceló (2019) and Pizarro et al. (2019), who propose that integrated processes of talent attraction, retention, and development reduce turnover and increase operational efficiency.

In the case of Tamay (2021), although regular talent management and average productivity were identified in a public entity, this highlights the importance of strengthening training and leadership strategies, which coincides with what Flores et al. (2018) proposes: that the human talent department must generate competitive advantages through the efficient organization of internal processes.

The models analyzed (Cuesta, Morales Cartaya, Werther and Davis, Harper and Lynch) offer different approaches that are also reflected in the results. Cuesta (2005), with his humanistic and person-centered vision, agrees with the studies that emphasize the importance of individual development as a driver of productivity. Morales (2009) reinforces the need to integrate HR processes with institutional strategy, especially in public contexts like Quiroz or Tamay.

In contrast, models such as that of Harper and Lynch (1992), with a more technical and sequential approach, are limited in the face of current needs for flexibility and innovation, where approaches such as those of Werther and Davis (2014), more systemic and interrelated, offer a perspective more consistent with the findings of the article.

In summary, empirical and theoretical evidence converge on the idea that proactive human talent management, aligned with organizational objectives and focused on human capital development, is key to increasing employee productivity. The studies reviewed reaffirm that sustained performance, quality, or competitiveness improvements will be challenging without a solid human talent strategy.

Conclusions

Human talent management is a determining factor in improving employee productivity, as it directly influences em-

ployee performance, motivation, and retention within the organization. Effective talent management optimizes available human resources and increases employee engagement, translating into continuous performance improvement and a greater ability to respond to environmental challenges.

Selection, training, evaluation, and compensation strategies must align with organizational objectives to ensure effective human capital management and contribute to the company's sustainable growth. When these processes are integrated into a strategic vision, they allow for the identification, development, and retention of key talent, generating value not only for the organization but also for the individual well-being of employees.

The analyzed models, especially those of Cuesta and Morales, offer integrative and strategic approaches that link employee personal development with operational efficiency and institutional competitiveness. Both models prioritize ongoing training, active employee participation, and consistency between human resources policies and the organization's overall strategy, demonstrating that a systemic approach is key to achieving sustainable results.

The literature lacks information on the practical application of talent management models in specific sectors, highlighting the need for further research that delves into their real impact on different organizational situations. Although the benefits of strategic talent management are recognized, empirical evidence is still lacking that shows how these models adapt and function in diverse contexts, especially in small organizations, the public sector, or developing economies.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: Roldán, T. M., & Pilozo, A. J. **Data curation:** Roldán, T. M., Pilozo, A. J., and Zirufó, B. V. **Formal analysis:** Roldán, T. M., Pilozo, A. J., and Zirufó, B. V. **Research:** Roldán, T. M., Pilozo, A. J., and Zirufó, B. V. **Methodology:** Pilozo, A. J., and Zirufó, B. V. **Supervision:** Roldán, T. M., and Zirufó, B. V. **Validation:** Pilozo, A. J., and Zirufó, B. V. **Visualization:** Roldán, T. M., and Pilozo, A. J. **Writing the original draft:** Roldán, T. M., Pilozo, A. J., and Zirufó, B. V. **Writing, review and editing:** Pilozo, A. J., and Zirufó, B. V.

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